
Impact of Current Legislative Framework of Jordan on the Trade Dispute Resolution in Local and International Arena

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Abstract:

The aim of the study is to identify the ways through which trade disputes at a different level of business operating in Jordan can be resolved with the application of Electronic arbitration. In this regard, Electronic arbitration is defined as a familiar and traditional form of arbitration that is considered a modern representation of resolving the disputes through using the alternative means for providing relief to the concerned parties. The applied method of this research is qualitative research, which is used for collecting and analyzing information of the research. The data of this research has been collected from different secondary sources, which include published data, journal articles, and books. The reason for using secondary data is to obtain in-depth knowledge and get valid data for the study. The primary objective of this study is to determine the extent to which the electronic arbitration's mechanism affects the disputes' settlement by considering the factors that are deemed as the means and mechanism. This has been followed by different companies electronically for preserving their rights in the global arena. In this research, the focus has been placed on the main ways in which the recent disputes of trade between companies can be handled locally, regionally and internationally through electronic arbitration. Moreover, another main aspect of this research is to demonstrate electronic arbitration's role in preserving businesses and organizations' rights along with establishing the confidence in different mechanisms and means in an optimal manner. Moreover, this study determines the extent to which the businesses and organizations prefer to resolve the dispute through electronic arbitration. Besides all different objectives of this research, this study evaluates the importance of electronic arbitration as an effective element for resolving conflicts in the global world. Moreover, the finding of this study identifies that electronic arbitration is more effective than the other traditional arbitration practices of business. Furthermore, a finding of the study reflected that businesses prefer to apply electronic arbitration, as it is more effective for resolving conflict in trade at different levels of business.

Keywords: Electronic Arbitration, Trade Dispute, Dispute Resolution, International Businesses, Local and Regional Businesses.

1. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this research is to identify different ways for resolving trade disputes arises at different levels of business. In this regard, Schanzenbach [1] identified that it is necessary to consider a viable and rapid solution for business; it may be much more viable for individuals because it is useful, effective and inexpensive. Based on the study of Lisman [2], it has been found that arbitration can help to find solutions to international trade disputes, especially among companies, firms, suppliers, and consumers in different countries. The world has been transformed into a digital global market, which requires all the practices with the intervention of technology in business practices. In this aspect, the concept of electronic arbitrations is considered as an effective element for resolving trade dispute in business. In this regard, Electronic arbitration is considered a traditional and ordinary arbitration's modern representation, which is one of the alternative means of resolving disputes [3]. In other words, it can be asserted that there is no such difference in electronic arbitration and traditional arbitration. The only difference that can be noticed is the way in which arbitration proceedings are conducted in different parts of the world virtually. According to the study of [4], the concept of electronic arbitration's can be defined from the contemporary view aspects of parties in relation to resolving the disputes, which can be considered relevant. Drahozal [4] identified that through using the method of arbitration as an alternative in trading on different levels effective dispute resolution method can be applied and the parties intend to negotiate the matters before filing any suits in the courts. This made it easier for the participants to make a settlement for trade dispute without involving in any complicated procedure for resolving trade disputes. In relation to this, Resnik [5] pointed out that trade disputes are resolved in a quick and adequate manner through considering the agreements signed between the parties. It is significant to note that there should be certain terms included in the agreement that is agreed by both parties. Moreover, the only

way to file an arbitrary claim is by including the arbitrary clause in the agreement signed [6].

In addition to this, Kim and Starozhilova [7] identified that arbitration has encountered a number of difficulties for its implementation as an effective alternative to the solution of business conflicts. Intrinsically, it can be noticed that both electronic arbitration and online arbitration are the same, as both of these contain the key element that arbitration should be conducted with the help of an international telecommunications network in an audio-visual manner without the physical presence of the parties to the dispute and the arbitrators in a particular place. Based on this, Wolff [8] pointed out that electronic arbitration could be differentiated through the use of communication's modern means that rely on information and communication technology. In this aspect, the electronic arbitration mainly includes the Internet, where the use of this network in a wide range of legal transactions, specifically commercial ones, has been present for creating a new type of electronic transactions or so-called electronic commerce.

2. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The arbitration is intended to resolve disputes relating to patrimonial rights available, this is a concept of the law that regulates the arbitration in a country. In this aspect, electronic arbitration consists in the creation of a judge not belonging to the normal jurisdiction, chosen by the conflicting parties, to settle disputes between them. The involved parties combine for resolving trade disputes among them based on extrajudicial means that can be used by the parties to resolve conflict arising from a business relationship of private assets available, given by the common choice of an arbitrator (judge) between them [9]. It has been identified that the markets' openness globally and a large number of commercial disputes created on a daily basis led the legislator to seek to develop the appropriate legislation to preserve the rights of companies and resolve their differences in a sound but also fast manner. The idea of this research is to explain the role of electronic arbitration in preserving the rights of companies and resolving their differences [10]. The focus of this study is to evaluate electronic arbitration that is extended from local to regional and finally international business level. Therefore, this research study would consider the main ways in which the current trade disputes between companies can be handled locally, regionally and internationally through electronic arbitration. While discussing and analyzing research problem, the main research questions that would be covered in this study are as follows:

- What are the legislative framework in Jordan and the main features from which the arbitration laws can be derived easily?
- What are the major aspects of the present legislative framework that have an impact on the

enforceability of the e-arbitration for the resolution of the e-commerce in Jordan?

- How can be the e-arbitration incorporate into the arbitration and e-commerce procedures in Jordan?

3. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

It has been identified that trade dispute in Jordan increasing in business that operated on a national and international level. The conflict that has been arisen in a market is difficult to resolve due to complex nature of the trade disputes. Therefore, this research aims to identify the importance of electronic arbitration for resolving conflicts among different businesses. It has been found that use arbitration in the conflicts generated by the businesses carried out by the Internet, it will be necessary to create a committee that would be responsible for registering electronic vendors and sites, provided they meet certain requirements [6]. This has demonstrated their suitability and express acceptance that settlement of disputes will be settled through arbitration. After registration and acceptance by the Board, an electronic certificate of reliability will be issued, giving the participants at least the guarantee that the seller has physical address and is legally constituted. Therefore, this research will contribute for an understanding role of arbitration for resolving trade dispute at different levels in of business operating in Jordan.

4. AIM & OBJECTIVES OF RESEARCH

This study aims to identify the impact of electronic arbitration for resolving trade disputes of the business into different levels including international, regional and local marketplace. Based on this, the focus of this study roamed around a legislative framework that is applied in Jordan for resolving conflict in the business. In relation to this, the research evaluates the mechanism of electronic arbitration, which affects the settlement of disputes by determining the factors, which are the means and mechanisms, that follow electronically and then determining the means by which companies should seek to preserve their rights. For attaining the aim of the study, this research is based on following objectives;

- To discuss the legislative framework in Jordan and its key features from which arbitration laws are derived.
- To identify the key aspect of the existing legislative framework
- To determine the effect of legislative framework on enforceability of e-arbitration for e-commerce dispute resolution in Jordan.
- To explore procedures through which e-arbitration be incorporated into e-commerce and arbitration in Jordan.

5. LITERATURE REVIEW

The main barrier in using arbitrage for conflict resolution of electronically generated business is that most electronic vendors have no physical address and are not legally incorporated. When an electronic buyer purchases a product from an electronic seller advertised on a particular sales site, the record of this, is in some cases false and when there are problems the buyer is watching their personal interest [11]. The only means of contact available is the seller's email, which after payment no longer accessible for the business. Once the stage of creation of the chamber responsible for the certification of the e-sellers and the websites have passed, and have to glimpse how in practice the arbitration operation for the business conducted with sellers established inside and outside the Jordan which we will suggest several elements. This includes the establishment of the arbitration procedure requires following the established specific law, which will be the primary source for the Chamber and Electronic Arbitration Courts. Additionally, Parsa [6] specified that for resolving trade disputes, the arbitration associated with voluntary is established by mutual agreement between the parties. Therefore, it is necessary that before carrying out the business seller and buyer electronically sign a contract that states the consent in submitting. In case of any trade dispute in Jordan, there is the conflict to arbitration.

In this aspect, it is important to understand that the buyer's certification should also be digital, so there should be a stimulus for the search for this certification, which is developed by the Federal regulatory authority of the country which is associated with the below elements that contain in the contract. The number of arbitrators, the legislation to be applied, the time for resolving the conflict, the recourse to the National Chamber and to which local court shall be subject shall basically be recorded in addition to the express agreement for conflicts to be decided by arbitration, each part. In this aspect, if there is any dispute arises at the local or regional level of Jordan than their need for resolving any conflict, the interested party should seek the local Arbitral Court, in which it is submitted by contract, the initiation of the arbitration procedure [12]. This practice has been supported by the aspect of the Arbitral Court that receives the complaint will communicate the defendant to appear on the day, time and place. This is already defined in the contract signed electronically, which is the court of the place that is established.

In addition to this, Barr, Moore [13] pointed out that based on the premise that buyer and seller are located in different geographic positions; it is not salutary that one or the other attend the forum of the other to perform the procedure, as stated, each one must appear in the Arbitral Court of his locality. In contrast to this, Khanji and Siam [14] pointed out that electronic arbitration made it easier for resolving conflict at international level as the business does not require going for arbitral court for any trade disputes due to presence of parties on digital medium for resolving business conflicts at

any level while dealing with business partners. Contrarily, Barr, Moore [13] identified that in traditional arbitration, the audiences would be performed by video-audio, in which it would be at each end, apart and the arbitrator. The number of arbitrators should be two, one in each Local Court. The decision is both jointly, if there is divergence, the sentence should be submitted, of ex officio, the National Chamber for decision. It may be established that there are not two arbitrators, but only one, located in a neutral Local Court. The courts must be equipped with equipment capable of performing the video-audio-audience.

On the other hand, Elkouri, Elkouri [15] is in the view that arbitration is considered as an alternative means for the judicial process in dealing with resolve trade disputes. It is considered to be an efficient, effective and economical process with respect to litigation practices that is mostly applied for resolving trade disputes in the region of Jordan. In the contemporary structure of international agreements, Schanzenbach [1] indicated that it has become a common thing modify the arbitration clause to resolve disputes that may arise in the contract. Similarly, Born [16] indicated that the "arbitration" means that if any, then voluntarily resort to the arbitral proceedings the parties involved in the trade agreement are in dispute. Therefore, the litigation and Law enforcement has been being carried out voluntarily on the basis of true principles [17]. For example, a Jordanian company 'X' runs a business with a French 'Y' company. The contract between them stipulates that any disagreement between the two parties resulting contract must be settled through an arbitration process in accordance with the provisions of Jordanian legislation, or in agreement with the International Chamber of Commerce (ICC) in Paris [18]. Therefore, if there is a dispute between the two parties, arbitration procedure agreed in the contract between the two parties before the actual conduct of business. However, if one of the two parties refers to the courts, the court before which the dispute is brought must refer the case to arbitration in accordance with the laws of their respective nations.

Notwithstanding, this is only possible if the national laws of the court state that which the case is heard recognize the place of arbitration between the disputing parties. This has to validate and giving credibility to the pre-negotiation agreement and the contract. In this aspect, legal doctrine addressed the interpretation and clarification of the concept of arbitration in its legal framework. Among multiple elements of legal doctrine, it has been found that some of these have defined it as a contractual system whereby the adversaries agree to resolve the dispute between them to arbitrators in order to separate them from ordinary judicial proceedings [19]. In addition to this, McLachlan, Shore [11] suggested that it is known as the arbitration that is intended to create a special justice through which disputes can be withdrawn from the hands of the judiciary to be resolved by arbitrators authorized to act. It is also known as a mixed system that begins with an agreement, then becomes a

procedure, and then ends with judgment. Furthermore, Frankel [20] stated that an agreement between two or more parties to bring out a dispute, or a number of disputes from the jurisdiction of the ordinary judiciary and entrusted to a body composed of one or more arbitrators to decide on binding jurisdiction. In this regard, it can be stated that the understand concept of arbitration is that it includes the two well-known traditional images [10]:

A. The arbitration agreement (Compromise): An agreement concluded by the parties separately and independent of the original contract between them, which requires the first resort to arbitration in the context of a dispute between them.

B. Clause Compromissoire: An agreement, which is contained in a contract that provides for the assignment of a future dispute or any dispute that may arise from this contract to an arbitral tribunal or arbitrator.

Notwithstanding, within the framework of the Jordanian Arbitration Law No. 31 of 2001, this distinction does not have any resonance [21]. The Jordanian legislator's approach is in line with the international approach in this regard, where we find no distinction in the New York Convention for the Recognition and Implementation of Foreign Arbitral Awards of 1958 with a consideration that the main difference between them is shown previously. It should also be noted that the Jordanian legislator in the arbitration law did not specify a clear definition of arbitration and did well, as the definition of the task of jurisprudence and judiciary, but between the conditions of the validity of arbitration in Articles IX and tenth thereof [12]. It is asserted that the contract of arbitration may be defined as a written agreement between two or more persons to withdraw the jurisdiction of the courts in the consideration of disputes expressly set out in the arbitration agreement and the granting of such jurisdiction to the person or entity to adjudicate this dispute called the arbitral tribunal.

Online Electronic Arbitration (E-Arb) is involved in a private dispute resolution process, which intervenes a neutral, impartial decision maker, arbitrator [13]. Moses [23] stated that arbitrator presided over by listening to both arguments and arguments, to achieve arbitration they have a binding decision. With the advent of information and communication technology, the process of network arbitration has arrived more and more popular and is being used by companies operating through the internet as an effective and inexpensive way compared to traditional court proceedings conventional arbitration [24].

The jurisprudence differed in this regard and was divided into two groups. The first was to consider the arbitration electronically if at one stage the modern means of communication were used while the other stages were carried out by traditional methods. The second group went to the conclusion that the arbitration is not electronic unless it is done through the means Electronic arbitration begins with an electronic contract, passes electronic arbitration

procedures that do not require physical attendance by the conflicting parties or arbitrators, and ends with issuing an electronic judgment therein. This seems to be the last opinion closer to the right of the first opinion because electronic arbitration means arbitration in which the technical means entered as an alternative to the meeting of arbitrators and parties to the dispute in one place [27]. The electronic judiciary of each of the parties to the conflict through such means as well. The attraction of the online process is its ease of accessibility, for example, a claimant can fill out a form on the Indian online arbitration website Cyber Tribunal, which is then sent to the other party. If the other party agrees to arbitration, they are requested to respond to the claim. When both parties undergo arbitration, the parties agree to comply with the award regardless of the outcome and final decision. In the instance of there being noncompliance, and in accordance with applicable laws and conventions, the injured party can request enforcement of the award. At present, there exist three main methods of arbitral procedure [25]:

1. The conventional arbitration procedures.
2. The use of the Internet for initial submissions within a conventional procedure.
3. The e-process involving an electronic arbitration agreement with digital signatures, video-conferencing, and an electronic arbitral award.

Based on the above discussion, it has been found that arbitration plays an essential role in resolving trade dispute among different parties. In relation to this, Najjar [26] defined international contracts as manifestations of the free will of concerned parties those are aiming at patrimonial relations or service. The elements of arbitration which are binding on two or more legal systems by force of domicile, nationality, principal place of business, place of the contract, place of performance, or any circumstance expressing an indication of applicable law [27]. Moreover, it has been found that international contracts still require greater and better regulation as a result of the increase in international trade relations, including electronic commerce. Thus, the importance of creating a more complete and current legislation on international contracts in Jordan is imperative. Based on this, Chickering [28] suggested that arbitration needs to be better presented to parties to an international contract so that it is effective when opting for this form of international trade dispute settlement. The reason for this is that there is still a disbelief or distrust that a private institution or agents can resolve the dispute in a fair manner.

In contrast to this, Farha et al., [29] identified that arbitration considers as a solution of controversy in international contracts that has been widely used because of indicators. This include distrust regarding the impartiality of the Judiciary when one of the disputing parties is foreign; the slowness of state processes; the confidentiality of the arbitration and the fact that the decision is rendered by experts in the subject matter of the litigation [30]. Thus, the

advantages and disadvantages of arbitration are its applicability and effective use that is used to suggest improvements in the arbitration process.

Moreover, it has been found that arbitral institutions may be created by inter-state agreements or may be private international ones [31]. The International Chamber of Commerce established in 1919, based in Paris, which is an institution governed by French law but is an international institution by the Federation of National Committees, formed in 47 countries, by trade associations. The Inter-American Commercial Arbitration Commission (ICAC) was established in 1933 and stays dormant for few years, which resumed its operation in 1979. There are, however, several national arbitration institutions, but by their practices, they can hardly be distinguished from those known as international organizations [32].

The consideration of arbitration while trading in the international arena is based on analysis of different factors. According to the study of Lewis [33], the use of arbitration has grown a lot in recent years, especially due to the expansion of international trade. However, mainly because of arbitration trade becoming better known, better organized and coming to be seen as a benefit for different business operating in Jordan [34]. In addition, there has also been an increase in the number of arbitration institutions throughout the world. These institutions have designed to promote the settlement of disputes between individuals and private individuals and the State that arises due to trade [35].

In relation to above discussion, it has been found from the study of Weiss, Klisch, and Profaizer, [36] that there are main motivators of the insertion of a contractual clause providing for the solution of conflicts through arbitration. The main element of this contains distrust among business, as to the impartiality of the Judiciary when one of the disputing parties is foreign. Fear of the state court to benefit the litigant with the same nationality, to the detriment of the foreigner. In relation to this, Schmitz [37] points out that international electronic arbitration would ensure the impartiality of the decision and the equitable treatment of the parties, regardless of their nationality. In addition to this, Piers and Aschauer [38] identified that there is often a steep slowness in state procedures, linked to positive procedural rules, which the parties cannot rule and change by agreement. Respecting the principles of public order, in arbitration, the parties are free to create a procedure. Moreover, Basak [39] specified that the confidential nature of the arbitration results in supporting knowledge of the litigation that is restricted to the parties and to the arbitrator. Therefore, being no publicity regarding the evidence produced the economic value of the dispute, the reason for the dispute, and the economic reflexes of the controversy [40]. Therefore, it has been found that confidentiality creates an atmosphere conducive to conciliation. In the Judiciary, there are only secrets of justice in cases provided by law.

6. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this research is to identify the ways, which can be applied to resolving trade disputes among business. The method for researching this topic is qualitative in nature, which has been obtaining through secondary sources. The applied methodology of this research is descriptive which identify different ways for resolving trade disputes with the influence of electronic arbitration. In this research study, the qualitative research method is used. The data has been collected from different secondary sources for understanding the electronic arbitration. The sources of data include multiple published journal, academic researchers and published reports through online libraries. It has been found that different techniques have been used for interpreting the techniques for comprehending and collecting the secondary data of a number of research studies. There are six main research designs that are used by different researchers for conducting research. Lewis has stated these research designs as follows: qualitative experiment, qualitative evaluation, field research, action research, document analysis and a case [42].

Through a spectrum of techniques and methods, the qualitative research could be characterized in an effective manner. Such techniques and methods point out the main object of the study. This helps the researcher in understanding the global view of the arbitration and the way businesses, individuals and organizations prefer to resolve the disputes through using the electronic arbitration. For achieving the research objectives, there is a particular methodology need has been applied for attaining a better understanding of the concept of arbitration and the way arbitral tribunals consider while resolving a dispute in a case. Moreover, this has contributed to attaining reliable outcome for the research study. In relation to this, Zikmund [42] have provided a comprehensible definition of research methodology stating that it is a general approach that research has taken in carrying out the research objectives [16]. In this paper, the qualitative research method is used for collecting the data and further analyzing different aspects that are linked with the electronic arbitration.

7. ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

From a global point of view, there are many studies on the broader aspects of electronics arbitration. It is perhaps considered by quiet few researchers to take a real look at reality Electronic arbitration and the incorporation of electronic methods into arbitration deal with [17]. Weiss, Klisch & Profaizer found the idea of Hill and studied the possibilities of electronic arbitration and procedural requirements to ensure online use technology, especially international arbitration [18]. However, Online Dispute Resolution (ODR) system including arbitration to the greatest extent possible [25]. In their study, researcher thinks that they can only focus on mediation because they find the data obtained from the situation is extremely difficult.

Investigators are reluctant to agree on the decision-making power to the arbitrator. Piers & Aschauer points out that the Internet is a document-only Arbitration, but online consumer arbitration is not common. The researchers think that the arbitration requires the actual personnel arbitrator, but the e-commerce dispute is also true. For now, this poses a serious challenge to credibility and feasibility. Therefore, they believe that arbitration is not the first choice for small and medium-sized e-commerce dispute, often the last resort in the ODR process when the two sides negotiate mediation failed [21]. Therefore, it is pointed out that arbitration cannot be automated involving the complexity of the case and the difficulty of validating all related issues file online. Subsequently, electronic arbitration emerged as a new image developed from traditional arbitration and is compatible with the specificity of electronic transactions and the disputes that result from it because arbitration is the same as the way electronic transactions are handled.

It has been identified from the study of Fayad and kazzi [31] that the role of electronic arbitration in preserving the rights of the company and to create and establish confidence in these means and mechanisms in an optimal manner that will achieve that goal. The key purpose of an arbitration clause in contract identifies to which extent the businesses and organizations prefer to resolve the dispute through electronic arbitration. In addition, evaluation of various literature indicating that in the current digital global world, electronic arbitration is considered as effective element while trading in an international arena.

In addition, it has been recognized that it is necessary to examine the legitimacy of arbitration from the point of view of public international law [25]. Through this, it has been identified that in which we find the limits imposed by the international public order. It indicates that an arbitral aspect under the will of an addiction of will is illegitimate and invalid. The arbitral element in international trade arising from an invalid arbitration agreement will certainly be invalid. Weiss, Klisch & Profzaizer [36] has been found that the execution of the international arbitration decisions depends on a political appreciation of convenience of the country. On the other hand, some authors affirm that the Jordan is responsible for the maintenance and execution of what it has agreed upon [24]; [18]. In this regard, it has been found that the spontaneous execution of the award is a matter of international responsibility. In case of any non-compliance, it may lead to recourse to a court such as for application of sanctions.

As electronic means is the distinctive character of electronic arbitration. It is necessary to complete the arbitration process in full through this means or is it sufficient to use modern means of communication at one stage to be considered electronically. The jurisprudence differed in this regard and was divided into two groups. The first was to consider arbitration electronically if at one stage the modern means of communication were used while the

other stages were carried out by conventional means [22]. The second group went to the conclusion that the arbitration is not electronic unless it is done entirely through electronic means, Electronic arbitration by electronic contract and electronic arbitration procedures do not require physical presence by the conflicting parties or arbitrators and ends with the issuance of an electronic judgment therein.

This seems to be the last opinion closer to the right of the first opinion because electronic arbitration means arbitration in which the technical means entered as an alternative to the meeting of arbitrators and parties to the dispute in one place [27]. The electronic judiciary of each of the parties to the conflict through such means as well. It cannot be said that the use of electronic means at some stages of arbitration makes it electronic because arbitration is not free from the use of modern means of communication at any stage. If the other party is notified by e-mail or sending some documents via e-mail or fax, such modern techniques cannot be dispensed with [32]. This may be confirmed by the fact that international arbitration centers operate on the Internet through their websites without describing their electronic arbitration today, but apply the rules of traditional arbitration. It has been found that arbitration arises from a contract and this has to be valid and lawful. The difference between private arbitration and public international arbitration is the problem in executing the arbitration aspect of trade in the country [8]. The purpose of this research is to identify the ways for resolving trade disputes in Jordan. It has been found that it is essential for involved parties to solve problems and conflicts of commercial interest, which can be solved by a useful mechanism that is the arbitration. Thus, the litigation will no longer be a judicial process that will be filed before the Judiciary and can be resolved through electronic arbitration.

8. CONCLUSION

From the above discussion, it has been found that electronic arbitration can be effectively used for resolving trade disputes in a different marketplace, which include regional, local and international. In this aspect, it can be concluded that different ways used by the companies when resolving the disputes virtually are the e-arbitration. In other words, the electronic arbitration is one of the key ways that can be helpful for the businesses to handle the disputes arising at local, regional and international level. In this study, the mechanism of electronic arbitration shows that the settlement of trade disputes through determining the factors, means and mechanisms has been helpful for the companies to preserve their rights.

In relation to this, the main aim of the study has been achieved through showing that the role of electronic arbitration in preserving the rights of the company and establishing confidence has been quite optimal that have helped in achieving the goals. The businesses and organizations choose the option of electronic arbitration to

resolve the dispute in order to minimize the time for managing all problems. Moreover, the effectiveness of the electronic arbitration identified which shows that in current time most of the companies that are operating in Jordan avoid face to face negotiations, and prefer to resolve the disputes through negotiating the issues online. The underlying reason is to make these practices convenient for the businesses.

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